

Twenty-four single plants falling in the range from $\bar{X} + 1$ SD to $\bar{X} + 2$ SD that also were better than check variety PMK1 in all characters were selected to forward to the F₃.

Metroglyph analysis could identify crosses and plants likely to produce superior progenies in early generations. The technique can be used while excising unidirectional selection in variable populations. □

Index score for different traits.

	Tillers per plant (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Plant height (cm)	Single-plant yield (g)
Range of means	5.2 - 11.2	17.0 - 23.7	64.8 - 76.8	11.9 - 15.1
Score 1 value <	6.7	18.7	67.8	12.75
Score 2	6.8 - 8.2	18.8 - 20.3	67.8 - 70.8	12.76-13.5
Score 3	8.3 - 9.7	20.4 - 22.0	70.9 - 73.8	13.6 - 14.25
Score 4 value >	9.8	22.1	73.9	14.25
\bar{X}	8.8	21.3	70.03	13.1
X + 1 SD	8.93	23.15	73.23	14.11
SE	0.04	0.56	0.96	0.31
CV (%)	1.5	8.67	4.57	7.7

Anther culturability of rice plants treated with male gametocide chemicals

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We evaluated the callus-forming abilities of anthers derived from F₁ rice plants of the japonica/indica hybrid IRAT13/H105 treated with the chemical hybridization agent G5 at 0.5 and 1.0 g/liter at 2 stages of panicle development (before and after meiosis). G5 is known to be effective on wheat and, to a lesser degree, on rice.

The number of anthers forming calli was three times higher in anthers treated with 1.0 g G5/liter before meiosis than in control (see table). Time of appearance of the first callus also was 6-8 d earlier. However, regenerability of induced calli did not differ significantly from that of the control.

The gametocidal effect of G5 on rice pollen sterility measured just before anthesis increased with increased application but remained weak. Spikelet sterility with 1.0 g G5/liter was 30-40% higher than control.

These results agree with results obtained in wheat.

The same experimental protocol was followed to assess the effect of ethephon at 2 and 4 g/liter on callus-forming abilities of treated anthers. In this case, discrepancies were noted among the results of the three replications. Spraying ethephon on donor plants does not appear to be a reliable way to increase rice anther culturability. □

Scatter diagram of metroglyph analysis using 12 crosses. ACRI, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988. 1-Norungan/MDU1, 2-Charumpuncha/MDU1 (5), 3 - ZR29/PMK1 (7), 4 - Arurakari/IR20 (11), 5 - Moongil samba/IR50 (11), 6 - IR29/IR50 (13), 7 - Charumpuncha/IR50 (9), 8 - MDU1/PMK1 (12), 9 - MDU1/IR50 (12), 10 - Norungan/IR50 (15), 11 - W1263/MDU1 (11), 12 - Moongil samba/MDU1 (8), C - PMK1 (check) (6). Figures in parentheses denote score index values.

Yield potential

Sources of variability in rice seed quality

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An inherent heterogeneity in rice seed quality exists between tillers of a plant and between plants in a population. When a variety is grown in different

Effect of male gametocide chemicals on callus formation ability of rice anthers.

Treatment	Callus-forming ability ^a (%)	
	Before meiosis	After meiosis
Distilled water (control)	5.6 a	5.4 a
0.5 g gametocide/liter	13.1 a	4.9 a
1.0 g gametocide/liter	17.8 b	3.8 a

^aAvof 2 replications, 1000 anthers each treatment. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

agroecological situations, seed quality also varies.

We studied the variability in seeds produced from different tillers in a plant, between plants in a population, and between populations produced in different parts of the Cauvery Delta Zone. Five varieties were tested: short-duration IR50, ADT36, and TKM9; medium-duration IR20; and long-duration CR1009.

Ten locations were selected, with 10 fields sampled in each location. For tiller and plant analysis, 10 clumps/field were used.

Seeds were collected at maturity and germinated in the laboratory. Percentage germination and seedling length were multiplied to calculate the vigor index. The results were pooled by location.

Between tillers and plants, variability was higher in seedling vigor than in germination. Variability in both germinability and seedling vigor was

almost equal across locations, irrespective of variety. Mean variability in germination and seedling vigor was 8.4 and 18% among tillers, 5 and 10% among plants in a population, and 23 and 24% among locations.

The higher variability between tillers than between plants might be due to different times of tillering (varying with water level) and times of anthesis and seed maturation. The difference

among locations might be due to different soil conditions, dates of sowing, and other environmental components.

Among the varieties, variability in seed germination among tillers was highest in CR1009; that among locations was highest in AD736 (Table 1). Variability in seedling vigor between tillers was highest in TKM9 (Table 2). □

Table 1. Variation in seed germination between tillers of a plant, plants in a population, and production locations. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Variation (%) in seed germination		
	Between tillers	Between plants	Between locations
IR50	7	5	21
ADT36	10	6	28
TKM9	4	2	24
IR20	7	6	20
CR1009	14	5	22
Mean	8.4	5	23
LSD: 3			

Table 2. Variation in seedling vigor between tillers of a plant, plants in a population, and location. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Variation (%) in seedling vigor		
	Between tillers	Between plants	Between locations
IR50	18	10	22
ADT36	16	9	21
TKM9	22	14	36
IR20	16	8	20
CR1009	18	10	23
Mean	18	10	24
LSD: 4			

Minimizing intravarietal variation in rice experiments

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Large variations in many morphological characters are observed within rice cultivars in field and greenhouse trials, even under uniform growing conditions. One reason may be differences in seed quality. We experimented with seeds of three varieties.

Bulk seeds of IR30, IR32385-37-3-3, and IR28211-43-1-1 (105-110 d) were harvested in 1988 dry season. Dried seeds were graded into poor, good, and high-density (HD) grains using distilled water and salt solutions of varying specific gravity. Seeds of each grade were separated into embryo, endosperm, and hull.

Total grain weights were similar, except in IR28211-43-1-1 (Table 1). Embryo weights of HD grains were significantly heavier than those of poor grains in all cultivars. In IR28211-43-1-1, embryo weights of the grades

differed significantly: large, heavy seeds had heavy embryos. Endosperm weights did not differ between good and HD grains, but were significantly heavier for both grades than for poor grain. Hull weight differed among grades in IR30 and IR28211-43-1-1.

Seeds of the three grades were sown in 4-liter pots containing 3 kg of

Maahas clay soil with added fertilizers, in a randomized block design with three replications and raised in the greenhouse.

At 25 DAS, seedlings from good and HD grains were significantly taller than those from poor grains. For most characters, the trends in IR30 and IR32385-37-3-3 were similar. In

Table 1. Characteristics of seeds of different quality.^a

Grain grade ^b	Weight (mg) per 100 grains			
	Embryo	Endosperm	Hull	Total
	<i>IR30</i>			
Poor	13.2 a	341.6 a	350.8 a	705.6 a
Good	17.9 b	1385.7 b	403.2 b	1807.3 b
High density	18.4 b	1549.6 b	438.0 c	2005.5 b
	<i>IR32385-37-3-3</i>			
Poor	23.7 a	908.3 a	351.4 a	1283.4 a
Good	25.5 ab	1481.9 b	407.9 b	1915.3 b
High density	27.1 b	1600.2 b	419.7 b	2047.0 b
	<i>IR28211-43-1-1</i>			
Poor	16.8 a	884.6 a	384.3 a	1285.7 a
Good	25.0 b	1626.2 b	441.0 b	2092.2 b
High density	29.4 c	1909.1 b	498.7 c	2437.2 c

^aMeans followed by a common letter in a column are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bPoor = sp gr ≤ 1.0, good = sp gr > 1.0- ≤ 1.20, high density = sp gr > 1.20.